

An advanced approach combining ssNMR with powder diffraction applied on newly synthesized isothiuronium salts

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Synopsis The article presents the synthesis of new tetrafluoroborate and bromide salts of isothiuronium compounds, followed by structural and spectroscopic studies, demonstrating that using ssNMR-derived intermolecular distances as restriction can increase the likelihood of finding the crystal structure model when solving crystal structure from powder diffraction data.

Abstract The article focuses on the structural study of isothiuronium salts and the application of intermolecular distances obtained by solid-state NMR (ssNMR) in determining crystal structures from powder diffraction data. The synthesis of three new tetrafluoroborate and two bromide salts of isothiuronium compounds is presented at the beginning, followed by structural and spectroscopic studies. Tetrafluoroborates were further analyzed by using advanced ssNMR techniques to obtain a set of intermolecular distances between $^{19}\text{F}\dots^{13}\text{C}$, $^{11}\text{B}\dots^{11}\text{B}$, $^1\text{H}\dots^1\text{H}$, and $^{13}\text{C}\dots^1\text{H}$ with the estimation of their precision. These distances were subsequently used as restraints in the crystal structure determination process from simulated powder diffraction data. The results show that using intermolecular distances obtained by ssNMR can increase the probability of finding correct solutions, creating new opportunities for the structural analysis of poorly diffracting compounds. This approach paves the way for solving more complex substances, such as solvates, cocrystals, or complex

polymorphs with many independent molecules, where traditional powder X-ray diffraction methods often reach their limits.

Keywords: NMR crystallography; powder diffraction; structure determination; isothiuronium salts

1. Introduction

Research focused on the synthesis and study of new compounds is inherently tied to thorough analysis, as understanding their properties and behaviours is critical. The ability to study these compounds is a crucial aspect of the process, with structural analysis being an essential part of the research. In such cases, single-crystal X-ray or electron diffraction with a precise atomic resolution is the method of choice for the first. However, not all compounds are suitable for this analysis, which then requires the use of other structural techniques such as powder diffraction and solid-state NMR (ssNMR).

In the case of powder diffraction (PD), several approaches exist to find a structural model. In addition to reciprocal space and dual space methods (Giacovazzo, 1998; Palatinus, 2013; Altomare *et al.*, 2009; Baerlocher *et al.*, 2007), which are commonly used in single crystal diffraction, direct space (DS) methods are widely used in PD to determine the structural model by applying global optimization principles. This is achieved by adjusting the position and conformation of molecular fragments within the asymmetric unit cell. Individual implementations of DS methods allow the definitions of geometric constraints to facilitate the search for solutions and reduce the computational time (David & Shankland, 2008; David *et al.*, 2006; Favre-Nicolin & Černý, 2002). Continued advances in the methodology of PD, coupled with programs using different approaches to determine crystal structure from PD data, have led to the structure determination procedure becoming applicable to relatively complex crystal structures (Hušák *et al.*, 2018, 2019; Fernandes *et al.*, 2007). The recent development in DS methods has led to the speeding up of the structure determination process using GPU abilities (Spillman & Shankland, 2021), reducing the degrees of freedom of the model by applying torsion angle restrictions (Kabova *et al.*, 2017) and combining PD with various techniques such as NMR, DFT, or theoretical prediction of the crystal structures (Habermehl *et al.*, 2022).

Despite continuous advancements, the current limitation in the complexity of DS methods, quantified by the number of degrees of freedom (DOF) — encompassing free torsional angles, as well as rotational and positional coordinates — remains at approximately 40 (Hušák *et al.*, 2018, 2019; Fernandes *et al.*, 2007). Additionally, the efficacy of this methodology is significantly constrained by the quality of the diffraction pattern. Beyond instrumental influences, the primary challenge lies in the sample quality. For example, the size of crystalline domains and the presence of strain broaden the

diffraction profile and reduce the resolution of the data, causing severe problems in solving the structure of even simple compounds (Schlesinger *et al.*, 2022).

In the case of ssNMR, crystal structure determination from ssNMR data is also possible. In general, this is due to the ability of advanced ssNMR techniques to measure intra- and intermolecular distances by analyzing dipolar interactions. Specifically, the method called NMR crystallography, which was first introduced in 2006 (Elena *et al.*, 2006), is based on the analysis of ^1H - ^1H spin-diffusion correlation signals combined with Monte-Carlo crystal structure simulations. An alternative approach is based on the experimental determination of ^1H and ^{13}C isotropic chemical shifts and their systematic comparison with the theoretical values DFT-calculated for the representative set of model structures derived by the crystal structure prediction (CSP) method (Salager *et al.*, 2010). The potential of this approach has recently been demonstrated on several systems with one molecule in the asymmetric part of the unit cell (Baías *et al.*, 2013; Brus *et al.*, 2016, 2018). However, the reasonable prediction of structural models of multicomponent solids such as cocrystals or polymorphic forms containing more symmetry-independent molecules requires the knowledge of key structural parameters, such as the mutual orientation of individual molecules and specific distances between them. For typical organic compounds, such information can be derived from the analysis of ^1H - ^1H double quantum coherences (DQC) and ^1H - ^{13}C heteronuclear correlations (HETCOR) (Brown, 2012; Van Rossum *et al.*, 1997; Hušák *et al.*, 2019; Brus *et al.*, 2022). For the compounds containing other NMR-active nuclei, the measurements of internuclear distances involving the nuclei with high natural abundance and high gyromagnetic ratio, such as ^{19}F , ^{11}B , ^{23}Na or ^{31}P , are particularly convenient.

Diffraction and ssNMR structural methods are frequently employed in a complementary manner to enhance and validate each other's findings. One of the typical bottlenecks of the X-ray diffraction techniques is the determination of the hydrogen atom position. In this case, ssNMR allowed the identification of salts, cocrystals, or tautomeric forms of compounds (Gumbert *et al.*, 2016; Smalley *et al.*, 2022). Combining ssNMR with powder diffraction is particularly advantageous, as it has enabled several crystal structures to be solved. The important role of ssNMR is also in the validation of the results found by powder diffraction. To study the synergy of NMR crystallography with powder diffraction in more detail, we kindly refer the reader to the article of Kenneth D.M. Harris (Harris, 2022), which briefly describes the synergy of NMR spectroscopy and XRPD.

In this article, we describe the preparation of three isothiuronium salts in the forms of bromide and tetrafluoroborate using anion exchange. Isothiuronium salts are a versatile group of compounds produced by S-alkylation of thiourea (Speziale, 1950). The variability of used thiourea derivatives and alkylating agents results in tunability of resulting salt properties. For this reason, they have found applications in numerous fields of chemistry. In organic chemistry, they are often used in the preparation of many groups of compounds such as thiols, sulfides, S-glycosides, selenoglycourils and cytotoxic 4-amino-5-cyano-2-sulfonylpyrimidines (Chauhan *et al.*, 2015; Magné & Ball, 2019; Wu *et*

al., 2016; Galochkin *et al.*, 2023; Khochenkov *et al.*, 2020). They also found application in the formation of bactericidal (Cohen *et al.*, 2017) and anticandidal (El-Zahed *et al.*, 2023) polymers as well as bactericidal micelle-forming surfactants (Valeeva *et al.*, 2021). Their antitumor activity against leukemia cells is particularly interesting, with a selectivity index higher than 20 (Ferreira *et al.*, 2017). The cause of cell death was found to be decreased levels of anti-apoptotic protein, causing DNA damage and mitotic arrest (Assunção *et al.*, 2019). Further studies also described activities against breast (Munaretto *et al.*, 2020), melanoma (Alcolea *et al.*, 2019), lung and prostate cancer cell lines (Alcolea *et al.*, 2016). Despite their extensive applications and significant biological activities, the detailed understanding of their crystal structures remains limited. Currently, 130 crystal structures of isothiuronium salts are documented in the Cambridge Structural Database CSD (Groom *et al.*, 2016).

We synthesised 2-(benzylthio)-4,5-dihydro-1H-imidazol-3-ium bromide (**1·Br**), 2-(benzylthio)-4,5-dihydro-1H-imidazol-3-ium tetrafluoroborate (**1·BF₄**), 2-(4-methylbenzyl)isothiuronium bromide (**2·Br**), 2-(4-methylbenzyl)isothiuronium tetrafluoroborate (**2·BF₄**), 2-(naphthalen-2-ylmethyl)isothiuronium bromide (**3·Br**), and 2-(naphthalen-2-ylmethyl)isothiuronium bromide (**3·BF₄**), an structurally described them with exception of already published **3·Br** (Eigner, 2020). Please note Fig. 1 with the molecular scheme.

Figure 1 Isothiuronium cations with their common labelling

This work presents a comprehensive structural and spectroscopic study of newly synthesized isothiuronium salts. We utilized their structural models to evaluate a novel combined approach of ssNMR and PD for crystal structure determination. These compounds are relatively simple in terms of degrees of freedom (DOF) and diffract very well, making it straightforward to determine their crystal structure by powder diffraction. Therefore, to test the abilities of the new approach, we applied it to calculated data with significant peak broadening to simulate nanocrystalline or strained sample, which makes the structure solution problematic. Specific ssNMR experiments were conducted to analyze ^{19}F - ^{13}C , ^{11}B - ^{11}B , ^1H - ^1H and ^1H - ^{13}C correlations, allowing us to estimate the corresponding intermolecular distances. These distances were then used as additional restraints in the crystal structure determination process to assess the efficacy of this new methodology.

2. Results and Discussions

2.1. Synthesis of isothiuronium compounds

Bromides **1·Br**, **2·Br** and **3·Br** were prepared using an equimolar ratio of thiourea (2-imidazolinethione) and arylbromide. The thiourea was dissolved (suspended) in acetonitrile 20 ml, and to the resulting solution (suspension), the corresponding amount of arylbromide was added. The reaction mixture was stirred using a magnetic stirrer at room temperature for 3 hours. The resulting precipitate was filtered off and dried.

Tetrafluoroborates **1·BF₄**, **2·BF₄** and **3·BF₄** were prepared from bromides using anion exchange. The isothiuronium bromides were suspended in 3 ml of distilled water with an equimolar amount of sodium tetrafluoroborate. The reaction mixture was shaken at 350 RPM at room temperature for one week. Then, the resulting solid was filtered off, washed with 3 ml of distilled water and allowed to dry. The resulting material was crushed in agate mortar with a pestle and shaken at 350 RPM at room temperature to dissolve any remaining inorganic salts for a week. Then, the material was filtered off and allowed to dry. The procedure was unsuccessful for samples **1·BF₄**, **2·BF₄**. These samples were then subjected to the same treatment, replacing the equimolar amount of sodium tetrafluoroborate and distilled water with 3 ml of saturated solution of sodium tetrafluoroborate. The transition under these conditions was successful. All the materials used in the isothiuronium salts preparation were purchased from commercial suppliers (Merck, TCI, Penta) and used without further purification.

2.2. Liquid NMR and IR spectroscopy

The prepared compounds were measured using ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR in DMSO-d₆. The NMR analysis confirmed the structure of prepared compounds, and in cases of **1·Br**, **1·BF₄**, **2·Br** and **2·BF₄**, did not show any significant differences between the anion structure. However, in the case of **3·Br** and **3·BF₄**, the difference in isothiuronium NH₂ groups signals, which are split into two positions in **3·Br** and again merged in **3·BF₄**. For detailed IR and NMR results see section S1 and Fig. S1 in Supporting Information.

2.3. Crystallographic study

All presented structures crystallized in monoclinic system, samples **1·Br**, **1·BF₄** and **2·Br** crystallized in centrosymmetric *P*2₁/*c* and *P*2₁/*n* space groups, while **2·BF₄** and **3·BF₄** crystallized in non-centrosymmetric *P*2₁ space group, see Table 1. In all cases, the asymmetric unit consisted of one isothiuronium cation and one anion, that is disordered over two positions in **2·BF₄**, see Fig 2. The published structure **3·Br** (Eigner, 2020) was included in the discussion for completeness. Due to the differences in atomic labelling, we have assigned common labels for all the cations that will be used for the description of structural differences in this work, see Fig 1. The bond lengths and angles vary little among the studied compounds and do not significantly differ from the expected values. Large.

difference between C(Me)-S and C(iTh)-S can be attributed to a partial double bond character of C(iTh)-S bond. The differences among the bond angles are more pronounced, with a clear tendency of bromides towards higher C(Ar)-C(Me)-S angle values, with an average value of 112.9° , while tetrafluoroborates tend to lower C(Ar)-C(Me)-S angle values, with an average value of 107.3° . Another significant difference can be observed among S-C(iTh)-N angles, with corresponding angles more obtuse in compounds **1·Br** and **1·BF₄** with average values of 127.7° and 121.1° , while for **2·Br**, **2·BF₄**, **3·Br** and **3·BF₄** the average values are 121.8° and 116.8° . These differences are most likely caused by the steric requirements of the five-membered ring present in structures **1·Br** and **1·BF₄**. Among the newly presented crystal structures, the C(Me)-S-C(iTh) angle exhibits small variance, with the largest deviation of 1.6° from the average value of 102.7° , while for published structure **3·Br**, the corresponding angle has the value of $96.99(16)^\circ$. For further information on bond lengths and angles, see Tables S1 and S2 in Supporting Information.

Figure 2 Asymmetric part of the unit cells of studied compounds with ADPs drawn at 50% probability level. The weakly occupied atoms are depicted as transparent with dashed bonds.

Figure 3 Figure 3 The overlay of isothiuronium cations. Cations from **1·Br**, **2·Br** and **3·Br** are depicted in pink, magenta and purple and cations from **1·BF₄**, **2·BF₄**, and **3·BF₄** are depicted in yellow, orange and red.

The possible rotation of two single bonds, C(Ar)-C(Me) and C(Me)-S, and one partial single bond, S-C(iTh), allows for conformational changes in the structures of studied compounds. Among the newly studied compounds, rotation about the partial single bond S-C(iTh) appears to be very constrained, with an average absolute value of torsion angle C(Me)-S-(iTh)-N2 at 168.6° and the largest difference of 5.3° in case of structure **1·BF₄**. In structure **3·Br**, the corresponding torsion angle is observed to be $110.7(3)^\circ$. The rotation about C(Ar)-C(Me) does not seem to follow any structure-related trend, but in all the structures, it is significantly different from planar arrangements, most likely due to steric interference with the hydrogen atoms of the aromatic ring. The average absolute value of C(Ar1)-C(Ar)-C(Me)-S torsion angle is 101.6° with the largest difference of 26.7° in structure **2·Br**. In the case of rotation about the C(Me)-S single bond, a clear structure-related trend is observed. Among the bromides, the isothiuronium cation bends significantly, with the average absolute value of C(Ar)-C(Me)-S-C(iTh) of 76.2° and the largest difference of 13.2° in the case of **1·Br**. While among tetrafluoroborates, the cations are almost straight, with the average absolute value of C(Ar)-C(Me)-S-C(iTh) of 168.6° and the largest difference of 5.3° in structure **3·BF₄**, see Fig 3. The straightening of isothiuronium cation in structures of tetrafluoroborates is most likely caused by the anisotropic behaviour of tetrafluoroborate anion, which allows the formation of strong hydrogen bonds only in specific directions. However, bromide anion can form hydrogen bonds in almost any direction, giving the weaker non-covalent interactions a larger influence on the cation conformation. For further instrumental and structural description see section S3 and Table S1 – S5 in Supporting Information.

Table 1 Summary of the SCXRD. The information on data collection, reduction and refinement

	1·Br	1·BF₄	2·Br	2·BF₄	3·BF₄
Formula	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₂ S·Br	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₂ S·BF ₄	C ₉ H ₁₃ N ₂ S·Br	C ₉ H ₁₃ N ₂ S·BF ₄	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ S·BF ₄
<i>M_r</i>	273.2	280.1	261.2	268.1	304.1
Crystals system	Monoclinic	Monoclinic	Monoclinic	Monoclinic	Monoclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>n</i>	<i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>c</i>	<i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>c</i>	<i>P</i> 2 ₁	<i>P</i> 2 ₁
<i>T</i> (K)	120	95	95	120	95
<i>a</i> (Å)	7.9876(2)	5.6817(4)	14.4689(6)	5.6075(2)	5.8011(3)
<i>b</i> (Å)	8.2176(2)	7.4235(5)	6.1901(3)	7.7882(3)	7.4127(6)
<i>c</i> (Å)	17.1250(4)	29.057(2)	13.3423(7)	13.8649(6)	15.2291(9)
<i>β</i> (°)	91.141(2)	91.387(6)	115.672(4)	95.836(3)	90.776(5)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1123.84(5)	1225.20(14)	1077.03(10)	602.37(4)	654.82(7)
<i>Z</i>	4	4	4	2	2
<i>D_{calc}</i>	1.615	1.518	1.611	1.478	1.542
<i>μ</i> (mm ⁻¹)	6.45	2.70	6.67	2.71	2.57
Crystal size (mm)	0.55 x 0.11 x 0.06	0.80 x 0.60 x 0.06	0.21 x 0.14 x 0.06	0.58 x 0.39 x 0.22	0.43 x 0.25 x 0.03
<i>θ</i> _{min} , <i>θ</i> _{max} (°)	5.17, 67.37	3.04, 74.71	3.39, 74.15	3.20, 67.52	2.90, 74.75
<i>θ</i> _{full} (98%) (°)	67.37	67.68	72.34	67.52	74.75
Measured reflections	13275	3923	3712	5004	8858
Independent reflections	2016	2368	2111	2130	2640
<i>R</i> _{int}	0.031	0.035	0.017	0.016	0.035
Observed reflections <i>I</i> > 3σ(<i>I</i>)	1903	2099	1998	2101	2595
<i>R</i> [<i>F</i> ² > 3σ(<i>F</i> ²)]	0.0241	0.0788*	0.0206	0.0291	0.0337
<i>wR</i> [<i>F</i> ² > 3σ(<i>F</i> ²)]	0.0723	0.2211*	0.0583	0.0776	0.0960
<i>R</i> (all)	0.0258	0.0834	0.0220	0.0293	0.0341
<i>wR</i> (all)	0.0737	0.2236	0.0601	0.0779	0.0964
<i>S</i>	1.43	1.04	1.11	1.64	1.86
Parameters	133	171	130	175	194
Restraints	2	8	4	4	4
<i>Δρ</i> _{min} , <i>Δρ</i> _{max} (e ⁻ Å ⁻³)	-0.34, 0.60	-0.71, 0.82	-0.22, 0.27	-0.17, 0.31	-0.38, 0.17
CCDC number	2383959	2383958	2383961	2383960	2383962

2.4. ssNMR spectroscopy

Before the ssNMR analysis, the purity of the samples was tested by phase analysis, see section S6 and Fig S23 - S25 in Supporting Information.

Sufficient spectral resolution allowing the explicit identification of individual atoms is the prerequisite needed for the reliable determination of interatomic distances from NMR spectra. However, as the structural differences between the aromatic carbons are relatively small, not all the signals are resolved in the ^{13}C CP/MAS NMR spectra (Fig 4A). This issue is much more complex for ^1H CRAMPS NMR spectra (Fig 4B), where the spectral resolution and chemical shift dispersion is strongly dependent on the structural diversity of the molecule and the presence of specific non-covalent interactions, e.g. hydrogen bonding. Nevertheless, by complementing with two-dimensional (2D) ^1H - ^{13}C FSLG HETCOR, ^1H - ^1H DQ/SQ CRAMPS and ^{19}F - ^{13}C CP/MAS NMR spectra and quantum chemical calculations (Brus et al., 2016), all the key signals were assigned reliably (for the details see Supporting Information S4, Tables S6-S8, Figures S9-S11).

Figure 4 A) ^{13}C CP/MAS NMR, B) ^1H CRAMPS, and C) ^{19}F MAS NMR spectra of the crystalline compounds **1·BF₄**, **2·BF₄** and **3·BF₄**. The molecular structures with the atom numbering are displayed above the spectra. Hydrogen atoms are numbered according to their parent atoms, so H2 is on C2, H3 on C3, and H7¹ and H7² on C7, etc.

Due to the methyl substitution, the structural differences between the aromatic protons are sufficient to be resolved in ^1H CRAMPS NMR. Consequently, all ^1H resonances can be distinguished for the **2·BF₄** compound (Fig 4B). For both **3·BF₄** and **2·BF₄** compounds, the signals of NH₂ protons are broadened due to the strong dipolar interactions with ^{14}N and due to the resonance effects involving NH and NH₂ groups. In the absence of methyl unit in the molecule of **1·BF₄**, the ^1H spectral

resolution is again slightly reduced. Nevertheless, at least two key resonances can be used to trace inter- or intra-molecular polarization transfers. Namely, it is the resonance of CH⁷ proton at 2.85 ppm and the signal of NH protons resonating at 8.21 and 7.94 ppm.

When looking at the BF₄⁻ counterion, the narrow symmetric ¹¹B MAS NMR signals at ca. -1 ppm detected for all systems (Supporting Information section S5, Figure S12) indicate tetrahedral coordination of the boron atom, the local geometry of which is highly symmetrical and probably effectively motion-averaged due to the tumbling of BF₄⁻ ion. This assumption is further supported by the ¹⁹F MAS NMR spectra (Fig 4C) in which the single narrow signals at ca. -145 ppm are detected. This finding thus indicates structural and magnetic equivalence of all fluorine atoms in BF₄⁻ anion caused by the reorientation of BF₄⁻ anions in the crystal lattice.

2.4.1. Measurements of ¹⁹F-¹³C interatomic distances

In NMR spectroscopy, information about interatomic distances r_{IS} is generally encoded in the strength of dipolar interactions D_{IS} , ($D_{IS} \sim 1/r_{IS}^3$). Since there is only one type of ¹⁹F atoms in the studied compounds, the simplest way to probe dipolar couplings between ¹⁹F and ¹³C heteronuclei is the variable contact time cross-polarisation experiment (CPVC). The strength of the dipolar interactions is then inversely proportional to the time constant T_{IS} , which describes the initial rate of the build-up of ¹³C NMR signals as formed by the cross-polarization from ¹⁹F spins. This polarisation transfer is described by the following function:

$$I(t) = I(0) / \left[1 - \frac{T_{IS}}{T_{1\rho}} \right] \left[e^{(-t/T_{1\rho})} - e^{(-t/T_{IS})} \right],$$

where $T_{1\rho}$ describes spin-lattice relaxation in the rotating frame. Since the time constant T_{IS} is proportional to the third power of interatomic distance, we first calibrated the $T_{IS} \sim r^3$ dependence by using the parameters determined for the crystalline molecular system with known local geometry (sodium trifluoroacetate) and derived a calibration function. Bearing in mind all the complexity of the cross-polarization transfer, which depends not only on interatomic distances but also on local mobility and the number of interacting spins (Kolodziejcki & Klinowski, 2002), the obtained time constants $T_{IS} = 0.5 \pm 0.1$ and 1.6 ± 0.2 ms and the corresponding distances ca. 1.4 and 2.5 Å roughly follow the expected dependence (see Supporting Information S5.1, Figures S14 and S15).

Fig 5A then demonstrates typical ¹³C{¹⁹F} CP/MAS NMR spectra measured at different ¹⁹F-¹³C cross-polarization mixing times (0.1 and 10 ms, **2·BF₄** compound). The build-ups of the corresponding ¹³C{¹⁹F} CP/MAS NMR signals are then presented in Fig 5B, and the complete experimental data collected for all compounds are summarized in Supporting Information Figures S5.2 and S16. The corresponding T_{IS} time constants together with the ¹⁹F...¹³C interatomic distances estimated using the derived calibration function are listed in Supporting Information, Table S9. Since the time constants T_{IS} were determined with an experimental error of ca ± 0.5 -0.7 ms, the uncertainty of the estimated

distances is at least about ± 0.2 Å. However, bearing in mind other contributions affecting the determination of the T_{IS} constants, such as motion averaging of dipolar couplings caused by the supposed rotation of the BF_4^- anion or the number of interacting spins, we rather suppose that the interatomic ^{19}F - ^{13}C distances are estimated with an experimental error of about ± 0.3 - 0.4 Å.

Figure 5 A) $^{13}\text{C}\{^{19}\text{F}\}$ CP/MAS NMR spectra of crystalline **2·BF₄** measured at two different cross-

polarization mixing times; **B**) ^{19}F - ^{13}C cross-polarization build-up curves created for carbon atoms #C1, #C4, #C7 and #C8; **C**) a typical ^{11}B - ^{11}B DQC build-up recorded for **2·BF₄** compound; and **D**) the dependence between the recoupling time at maximum DQ coherence intensity, t_m , and the interatomic $^{11}\text{B}\dots^{11}\text{B}$ distance, r .

For the **2·BF₄** compound, for instance, the fastest increase in the signal intensities was observed for carbons #C7 and #C8, for which the cross-polarization ^{19}F - ^{13}C rate constant T_{IS} was determined to be 2.8 and 3.3 ± 0.5 ms, respectively. This indicates the shortest interatomic distance of about 3.1 - 3.3 ± 0.4 Å. A bit slower signal build-up with the T_{IS} of 6.6 ms was observed for #C1 carbon, which reflects a bit more distant ^{19}F - ^{13}C spin pair of ca. 4.2 ± 0.4 Å. The slowest build-up characterized by the longest T_{IS} time constant of 8.6 ms was then detected for #C4 carbon, reflecting the interatomic distance of about 4.6 ± 0.4 Å. Overall, the short-range one-bond F...C distances of ca. 1.4 ± 0.2 Å are characterized by T_{IS} constants of about 0.5 ms, while the two bond spin pairs of ca. 2.5 ± 0.2 Å by the T_{IS} constants of about 1.5 ms. The medium-range F...C distances up to ca. 3.0 - 4.0 ± 0.4 Å are typically reflected by T_{IS} ranging from 2.7 to 5.0 ms, whereas the long-range distances about 4.2 - 5.0 ± 0.4 Å by T_{IS} of about 6-10 ms.

2.4.2. Measurements of ^{11}B - ^{11}B interatomic distances

^{11}B nuclei, owing to their high gyromagnetic ratio and high natural isotopic abundance, are particularly suited to probe long-range dipolar contacts in multicomponent systems, and as demonstrated previously, the evolution of ^{11}B - ^{11}B double-quantum coherences (DQC) allows determining $^{11}\text{B}\dots^{11}\text{B}$ distances up to ca. 7 Å (Brus *et al.*, 2017; Hušák *et al.*, 2018). Such a typical

build-up of ^{11}B - ^{11}B DQ coherence showing a maximum at ca. $t_m = 3.2 \pm 0.4$ ms is demonstrated in Fig 5C for **2·BF₄** compound. By applying the previously derived calibration function, $r = 0.23t_m^{0.38}$, where r represents the $^{11}\text{B}\dots^{11}\text{B}$ interatomic distance and t_m is the recoupling time at which DQC reaches maximum intensity (Fig 5D), the t_m values indicate a typical $^{11}\text{B}\dots^{11}\text{B}$ interatomic distances of ca. 5.3 ± 0.4 Å. When considering the existence of a distribution of interatomic distances, for instance, by the presence of two B...B pairs, then the corresponding typical interatomic distances could be ca. 5.0 ± 0.4 Å and 5.5 ± 0.4 Å. The distances obtained this way for all the investigated compounds are summarized in Supporting Information Table S10. However, also in this case the determined B...B distances must be considered as rough estimates. This is particularly because the evolution of double-quantum coherences of ^{11}B is affected by undecoupled interactions with ^{19}F spins.

2.4.3. ^1H - ^1H DQ/SQ CRAMPS NMR correlations

If the resolution of ^1H CRAMPS spectrum is good enough, then the corresponding 2D ^1H - ^1H DQ/SQ CRAMPS NMR spectra (Fig 6) can be used to trace ^1H - ^1H interatomic dipolar contacts in order to obtain additional information on the corresponding distances. However, although the ^1H - ^1H DQ/SQ CRAMPS NMR correlation spectra show almost complete set correlation signals (Fig 6), the majority of the detected correlations reflect useless intramolecular short-range $^1\text{H}\dots^1\text{H}$ dipolar contacts. In this case, it is more useful to examine the autocorrelation signals of well-defined proton species. Since the autocorrelation signals are only evolved when the corresponding atoms are sufficiently close together (no more than about 5.0-5.5 Å), their presence or absence basically defines the molecular arrangement in the crystal lattice. For example, for the **2·BF₄** compound, we focused on the autocorrelation signals involving aromatic protons H2, H5, H3 and H6, whose signals are well separated (Fig 6A).

Figure 6 ^1H - ^1H DQ/SQ CRAMPS NMR correlation spectra of **2·BF₄** A); and **1·BF₄** B) compounds measured at spinning frequency of 10 kHz and 4 recoupling loops.

Specifically, the presence of strong autocorrelation signals H3-H3, and a bit weaker autocorrelation signal H6-H6 indicates that the corresponding interatomic distances are less than ca. 4.5 Å, whereas the absence of H2-H2 even recorded with the longest recoupling time indicates that the corresponding intermolecular interatomic distance must be longer than ca. 5.0-5.5 Å (Brus *et al.*, 2016). Similarly, for the **1·BF₄** compound, we focused only on the analysis of the ¹H-¹H correlations involving the signals of CH₂ proton H7¹ (Fig 6B). Besides the expected very short intramolecular H7¹...H7² pair of the distance of ca. 1.8 Å, we identified the second short-range pair (probably intermolecular) involving proton H2. Bearing in mind the relatively high intensity of the correlation signal and relatively short recoupling times the distance in this H7¹...H2 pair can be estimated in the range of ca. 2.0-2.5 Å. All the recorded spectra and extracted distances are summarized in Supporting Information Figures S17-S19 and Table S11.

Figure 7 Expanded regions of the ¹H-¹³C FSLG HETCOR NMR spectrum of the **2·BF₄** compound measured at 400 μs cross-polarization contact time

¹H-¹³C HETCOR MAS NMR correlation. In the same line as for the ¹H-¹H correlation experiments, the useful information about the interatomic distances between ¹H and ¹³C nuclei could be derived from the ¹H-¹³C HETCOR MAS NMR spectra only for the **2·BF₄** system, which had a very good resolution in the ¹H dimension (Fig 7). Specifically, we monitored the ¹H polarization transfer from methyl protons (H9). This is because the ¹H resonances of methyl groups usually exhibit long lifetimes, allowing the large distances to be bridged. In addition, the intramolecular distances between H9 protons and C7 and C1 carbon atoms of about 6.2 and 4.7 Å are too large to allow efficient polarization transfer. Consequently, the H9-C7 correlation signal detected within the 400 μs CP mixing time (Fig 7, Supporting Information Figure S20) must reflect intermolecular contacts. Following the literature data (Van Rossum *et al.*, 1997; Brus & Jegorov, 2004), the corresponding interatomic distance is about 3.5-4.0 Å, because the intramolecular H9-C2 correlation signal reflecting the similar distance is of a comparable intensity. In this regard, the correlation signal H9-C1 then seems to indicate intermolecular dipolar contact reflecting similar interatomic distance (<4.0 Å), because the corresponding intramolecular distance is considerably larger (4.7 Å).

In summary, by using a range of experimental techniques, we obtained a representative set of intermolecular distance restraints data involving $^{19}\text{F}\dots^{13}\text{C}$ pairs (12x), $^{11}\text{B}\text{-}^{11}\text{B}$ pairs (3x), $^1\text{H}\text{-}^1\text{H}$ pairs (7x) and $^{13}\text{C}\text{-}^1\text{H}$ pairs (2x) which was subsequently used for refinement of XRPD data, see Table 2 and (Supporting Information Table S12).

2.5. Applying and testing the combined approach of ssNMR and PD

We modified the source code of the FOX (Favre-Nicolin & Černý, 2002) program to apply the distances obtained by ssNMR to the structure determination process from PD data. The global optimization algorithm in FOX uses a cost function (CF) to evaluate the quality of the model and searches for a solution by minimizing the CF. The CF includes the quality of the profile fit and several other terms that reflect the additional restraints applied. The equation of the cost function used in the FOX program can be written as:

$$CF = \chi_{profile}^2 + s_1\chi_{restraints}^2 + s_2\chi_{atibump}^2 + s_3\chi_{valence}^2,$$

where individual χ^2 are terms for agreement of the profile fit, geometrical restraints, anti-bump and bond valences, and s_i are their scale factors. We took advantage of this definition, and we introduced an additional parameter reflecting the agreement of the intermolecular distances (χ_{imd}^2) defined in the same way as $\chi_{restraints}^2$ (Favre-Nicolin & Černý, 2004), and its scale factor s_4 :

$$\chi_{imd}^2 = \sum_i \left(\frac{d_i - (d_{i0} \pm \delta_i)}{\sigma_i} \right)^2,$$

where d_i is the actual value, d_{i0} is the defined restrained value, δ_i means the range without penalty, σ_i plays the role of the precision of the defined value, and *imd* abbreviates the term intermolecular distances (IMD).

The intermolecular distances obtained by ssNMR, summarised in Table 2, were used in the crystal structure determination process of compounds **1·BF₄**, **2·BF₄** and **3·BF₄** from simulated X-ray powder diffraction data. These compounds are relatively simple to solve because they have only 15 degrees of freedom. This also confirmed the initial testing with simulated data corresponding to the laboratory instrument (FWHM = 0.1° 2 θ), where almost all runs executed with 10⁶ trials ended up with a correct solution. With such a resolution and simple compounds, the structure solution process from powder data is straightforward, and additional information is unnecessary. The situation may be complicated with significant peak broadening induced either by stressed crystallites, small particles or a combination of both, and the crystal structure determination process may fail even for such simple compounds. To simulate the situation with data of bad quality, we generated two theoretical XRPD patterns for each of **1·BF₄**, **2·BF₄** and **3·BF₄** compounds in the program Mercury (Macrae *et al.*, 2020) (from 4° to 50° 2 θ , step size 0.01, $\lambda = \text{CuK}\alpha_1$) with significant peak broadening. We set FWHM to 0.5° and 1.5° 2 θ to simulate bad and extremely bad diffraction data. The success rate of structure

solutions from such bad-quality data dropped down rapidly to approximately 2% - 50%, see results of normal runs in Fig 8. Subsequently, these patterns were used step by step to solve the crystal structures with and without using the additional IMDs (Table 2) obtained from NMR crystallography. The initial models for structure determination using the DS approach in program FOX were taken from already solved structures presented in this work and were randomized in their molecular positions and conformations. In this way, we obtained one randomized model for every compound that was used as a starting model for all testing runs to ensure the same starting conditions for all tests. The parallel tempering algorithm for the structure solution process was set to perform 1000 runs for every parameter set, each with 10^5 trials. Parameters s_4 , σ and δ in χ^2_{imd} , can be set individually, and their values will affect the final success rate of the calculation. The scale s_4 gives the overall influence of χ^2_{imd} for the resulting CF, and σ in this parabolic formula is actually another representation of the scale. Therefore, for simplicity in testing, only different values of the parameter s_4 were tested, while the values of σ were set to 1, and δ values were set according to the precision of the ssNMR distances in Table 2. Four parameter sets were defined for every compound: one normal run that did not use the IMDs and three that used IMDs listed in Table 2 and differing only in the scale factor s_4 , which was set to 10^4 , 10^5 , and 10^6 . The aim was to estimate the influence of the scale factor on the structure solution process. Every result list was classified based on the similarity to the reference structure obtained by SCXRD. The similarity was evaluated as the RMSD value of minimal distances of atomic positions in the overlapped molecular clusters that also contain anions using the modified code of CrystalCMP (Rohlíček & Skořepová, 2020).

The results show that using IMDs in the structure determination process resulted in comparable or higher success rates than without their use. There is a notable difference in the success rate between the datasets with $\text{FWHM} = 0.5^\circ$ and $\text{FWHM} = 1.5^\circ$, where the maximal success rate was 1.2 to 2.4 and 2 to 2.8 times higher, respectively, compared to a normal run, see Table 3. IMDs were more advantageous for low-resolution datasets where structure determination is rather difficult due to the lack of structural information in the powder diffraction data. In these situations, the additional structural restrictions helped overcome this problem and significantly increased the probability of finding the correct solutions. For the scale factor s_4 , we can conclude that too low a value may almost not affect the success rate, while too high a value may make it worse (Fig 8 **1•BF4**). In the case of **3•BF4**, the distance F...C1 was estimated from the ssNMR experiment as $4.5 \pm 0.5 \text{ \AA}$, but the distance from the SCXRD was found to be $5.112(3) \text{ \AA}$. The difference, including accuracy, is approximately 0.1 \AA , resulting in slightly higher absolute CF values for all individual correct solutions. However, its influence on the success rates compared to the **1•BF4** and **2•BF4** compounds is not notable, see Table

3. The results are depicted in Fig. 8, where all results of every determination process were sorted based on their similarity to the reference structure.

Figure 8 The individual graphs show a sorted list of solutions (only the N best solutions out of 1000 are depicted for clarity in each graph) of the structure determination process of **1·BF₄**, **2·BF₄**, **3·BF₄** from simulated XRPD data and their similarity with the reference crystal structures as an RMSD value of the closest atomic positions in the overlapped molecular clusters. Scales 1, 2, and 3 mean $s_4 = 104$, 105 and 106. The patterns with FWHM = 0.5° (left) and FWHM = 1.5° (right) were used. Approximately at RMSD = 1 Å, the solutions lost their similarity with the reference structure. A black line in all graphs notes this value. Individual number of solutions with RMSD < 1 Å are specified in Table 3.

Table 2 Intermolecular distances in Å obtained from ssNMR measurement and their comparison with distances measured from single-crystal X-ray diffraction model that satisfy the ssNMR range

	ssNMR	SCXRD
1·BF4		
F...C2,6	4.9 ± 0.4	3.416(6)*, 4.134(7)*, 4.785(7), 4.837(6), 5.076(6)
F...C7	3.4 ± 0.4	3.287(8), 3.257(6)
F...C8	3.8 ± 0.4	3.594(7), 3.692(8), 3.693(7), 3.903(6)
F...C9,10	3.1 ± 0.4	3.092(6), 3.104(7), 3.149(7), 3.237(7), 3.246(6), 3.276(6), 3.282(6)
B...B	4.8 ± 0.4	5.073(8)
2·BF4		
F...C1	4.2 ± 0.4	4.15(3), 4.254(17), 4.26(2), 4.48(2), 4.574(18)
F...C4	4.6 ± 0.4	4.524(17), 4.79(2), 4.99(2)
F...C7	3.2 ± 0.4	3.39(2), 3.45(2)
F...C8	3.3 ± 0.4	3.62(3), 3.63(2)
B...B	5.0 ± 0.3	5.11(4), 4.87(3)
	5.5 ± 0.3	5.61(2), 5.607(19)
3·BF4		
F...C1	4.5 ± 0.5	5.112(3)*
F...C3	3.4 ± 0.4	3.388(2)
F...C11	3.2 ± 0.4	3.186(3)
F...C12	3.4 ± 0.4	3.406(2), 3.409(3), 3.493(3), 3.579(3)
B...B	4.5 ± 0.4	4.698(4)
	5.8 ± 0.4	5.801(3)

*the closest A...B distance, but does not satisfy the condition.

Table 3 Number of solutions with RMSD difference < 1 Å from the reference structure and their success rate multiplicity in parentheses compared to the number of solutions of normal runs.

	1·BF4		2·BF4		3·BF4	
	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM
	0.5°	1.5°	0.5°	1.5°	0.5°	1.5°
normal run	221	23	168	77	526	126
$s_4 = 10^4$	258	21	259	136	602	217
	(1.2x)	(0.9x)	(1.5)	(1.8x)	(1.1x)	(1.7x)
$s_4 = 10^5$	282	51	410	181	651	259
	(1.3x)	(2.2x)	(2.4x)	(2.4x)	(1.2x)	(2.1x)
$s_4 = 10^6$	212	34	399	213	584	249
	(1.0x)	(1.5x)	(2.4x)	(2.8x)	(1.1x)	(2.0x)

3. Conclusions

In this study, we have synthesized six isothiuronium salts in the forms of bromide and tetrafluoroborate (**1·Br**, **2·Br**, **3·Br**, **1·BF₄**, **2·BF₄**, **3·BF₄**). We described them by IR and liquid NMR and, with the exception of the already published **3·Br** (Eigner, 2020), we also described their crystal structures using SCXRD. Additionally, the three tetrafluoroborates (**1·BF₄**, **2·BF₄**, **3·BF₄**) were analysed using a combination of ssNMR techniques, including various 1D and 2D correlation experiments. After a careful calibration of NMR data against known standards, a comprehensive set of interatomic distances between ¹⁹F...¹³C, ¹¹B...¹¹B, ¹H...¹H, and ¹³C...¹H were provided together with a rough estimation of their precisions. The intermolecular distances between non-hydrogen atomic types were then used in the crystal structure determination process from the simulated powder diffraction data. The results confirm that the combination of ssNMR spectroscopy and PD analysis can be beneficial, and using intermolecular interactions as additional restrictions in crystal structure determination increases the probability of finding a correct solution.

This study highlights the synergistic benefits of integrating multiple experimental and computational techniques, significantly expanding the applications of NMR crystallography and powder diffraction to badly diffracting compounds. Extending it to more complex compounds such as solvates, cocrystals, or complex compounds with many symmetry-independent molecules is the next promising step offered by this approach.

Conflicts of interest The are no conflicts of interest.

Data availability Crystallographic data can be obtained from CCDC (<https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/structures/>) using CCDC numbers noted in Table 1. NMR, IR and PXRD are mostly presented in the Supplementary Information. Alternatively, they can be requested from the corresponding author.

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